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GALAXY EVOLUTION ACROSS TIME

An extremely rich group of starbursts and AGNs at a $z=3.1$ proto-cluster core

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Outline

0. Introduction

- Target field: $z=3.09$ proto-cluster core
- ALMA Deep Surveys in a biased region

1. ALMA Deep Field in SSA22: ADF22

- 'unbiased' census in a biased field: cold dust

2. molecular ALMA Deep Field: mADF22

- 'unbiased' census in a biased field: molecular gas

3. Summary

Target: SSA22 Proto-cluster

§ Surface number density map of $z=3.09$ LAEs

SMGs in the galaxy overdensity?

- Yellow (Blue) circles: $z \sim 3.1$ AzTEC (SCUBA) SMGs
- SMGs appears to reside in the proto-cluster.

New mm window: ADF22

§ AzTEC 1.1mm map of the SSA22 field

Tamura et al. 2009; HU et al. 2014

1. ALMA Deep Field in SSA22 at 1.1mm

1.1mm Map

Frequency	263 GHz (1.14mm)
Area	7 arcmin ²
Angular res.	0.5''
RMS	60 uJy/Beam
Detection	18 at 5sigma

HU+17b

[OIII]5007
by **MOIRCS**

Redshifts of ALMA sources

ADF22.11 at $z=3.093$

Kubo, HU, et al. 2016

ADF22.16 at $z=3.085$

CO(3-2)
by **LMT**

ADF22.1 at $z=3.0915$

Yun et al. in prep

- 12/18 ALMA sources are at $z=3.085-3.097$.
- 4/18 may be at $z=3.1$, but no secure spec- z .
- One is at $z=2.1$, another is at $z>4$.

Multiplicity of 'classical' SMGs

HU+17b

- Multiple SMGs consist some of bright 'classical' SMGs.
- Physically associated SMG groups can account for some portion of them.

SMGs in the cosmic structure

- An extremely rich SMG cluster are found in the node of a cosmic web.
- The most active star-formation and SMBH growth simultaneously occur at the center of the $z=3.1$ proto-cluster.

2. ALMA Deep Field in SSA22 at 3mm (for CO(3-2))

Observations

ALMA
Band3

Frequency	84~86 GHz
Area	~6 arcmin ²
Angular res.	0.9" x 0.8"
Detection	8 at 5sigma

- CO(3-2) at $z \sim 3.09$ is covered with one spw.

CO(3-2) Spectra of ALMA sources

HU+17c, in prep

- CO, [CII] lines are strongly required for such galaxies.

Molecular Gas Mass Density

★ ADF22

- Molecular gas mass density is also high at the proto-cluster core.
(We assume $\alpha_{\text{CO}} = 1.0 \text{ Msun (K km}^{-1} \text{pc}^2)^{-1}$) (Bothwell+13))

CO Luminosity vs IR Luminosity

Summary

- SSA22 Field is a nice target to investigate the co-evolution of galaxies and cosmic structure. A 2'x3' 'contiguous' region at the center is covered by ALMA band 6 and band 3.
- We found lots of dusty starburst galaxies at $z_{\text{spec}}=3.09$. This means that
 - Multiplicity is caused by 'physically associated' dusty star-forming galaxies at least at the $z=3.09$ proto-cluster.
 - Both intense star-formation and rapid SMBH growth occur at the node of the 3D cosmic structure simultaneously.
- The 'blind' CO(3-2) survey is uncovering the molecular universe. For instance,
 - Molecular gas mass density at the proto-cluster core appears to be much higher than the general field.
 - Bright SMGs in ADF22 show lower SFE than typical SMGs. Rich gas supply may partially account for the over abundance of SMGs.